

CONVEY THE NATIONAL SPIRIT IN TRANSLATIONS

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Annotation: *This article provides insights into the situations in which a translator is required to fully convey the meaning of words that mean the concepts of life of peoples who do not have an alternative interpretation in their own language, and to solve a number of complex tasks in this regard. Words denoting objects, concepts and events belonging to a certain people, serve as a support in the process of proving the material and spiritual life of the heroes described to the author of in a hackneyed, national form. Realities are one of the main means of determining the national character of a work of art. In a sense, it is possible to solve the problem of translation, which requires a solution, such as the re-creation of the national fabric of the original story in another language.*

Key word: *alternative interpretation, concepts of life of peoples, complex tasks, objects, concepts and events, author of the story, national form, alternativeity in translation.*

Introduction: Translation is the transfer of new linguistic material while preserving its unity, which in fact means that it reflects its artistic vocabulary as a whole; therefore, the specificity of the translator's work expressed in the linguistic elements is also reflected in the national science.

Is it possible to establish the individuality of a translator without his national characteristics?

After all, he creates translations for the future of the Uzbek people.

Moreover, national identity is known only in language, because translation is not just about replacing one linguistic form with another. Consequently, the notion of "translator's individuality" includes the notion of "national identity." Words denoting objects, concepts and events belonging to the people serve as a support in the process of proving the material and spiritual life of the heroes described by the author novel in a hackneyed, national form. Realities are one of the main means of defining the national character of a work of art an translation problem can be solved in a certain sense. By the way, it should also be noted that specific words and term concepts should be distinguished from each other.

Terms are the basis of scientific vocabulary; their scope of use is special scientific literature. Specific words are typical of most fiction, they are local, historical, national components. While terms are the common property of all dictionaries in the world, words are only artificial terms that have come into being on their own. Adequate interpretation of words and sentences that express the concepts of people's lives in another language is one of the constant problems of every artist in the translation of the artistic style of the work. It should be noted that no theoretical study of this problem has developed a single rule for the translation of realities, because translation is a creative process and such ideas are not expected. We also want to suggest ways to overcome various random obstacles that may occur in practice in the translation of specific words by expressing our scientific and organizational considerations and conclusions on this topic.

Material and methods: In order to reconstruct the proper words in the language of translation, in our opinion, it is necessary to take into account the following: the function of the proper word in the text, the load of meaning; the relationship of original words in the original language and the language of translation; peculiarities of original and translated languages - their ability to work, literary traditions; comprehensibility of the specific word included in the translated language to the reader.

Translating realities into context, not only figuratively, but also in material terms, using a variety of methods and taking into account their original features, allows you to draw objective conclusions. In the process of translating the means of expressing the concepts of life of peoples into another language, first of all, it is to give a new language in the material, while preserving their unity in a particular text, which means that the pocket reflects the artistic reality as a whole; therefore, is it possible to see the creativity expressed in linguistic elements without national-nominal features? After all, he creates a translation for the well-being of the Uzbek people and for the people themselves. Moreover, national identity is known only in language, because translation is not just about replacing one linguistic form with another.

Consequently, the concept of interpreter individuality also includes the concept of "national identity". In the language of every nation there are words that, although in fact they are not distinguished by separate signs, it is not always possible to translate them into another language according to the rules of translation. Words denoting objects, concepts and events belonging to a certain people serve as a support to the author of the work in the process of proving the material and spiritual life of the heroes in a hackneyed, national form. The

translator is required to fully convey the meaning of such words, which mean the concepts of life of peoples who do not have an alternative interpretation in their language, and to solve a number of complex problems associated with it.

Realities are one of the main means of determining the national character of a work of art. In exchange for the alternative re-creation of words that mean the concepts of peoples' lives in translation, the problem of translation, which must be solved in a certain way, such as the re-creation of the national fabric of the original acar in another language, can be solved. At the same time, it should be noted that the specific words and terms should be distinguished from each other. Terms are the basis of scientific vocabulary; their scope-specific scientific literature. Specific words are typical of most fiction, they are local, historical, national

While the terms are the common property of all the properties in the world, the specific words refer only to the language of the people from which they originated.

It is possible to determine how skillfully they translated into another language. Adequate interpretation of words and sentences that mean the concepts of life of peoples is one of the constant problems faced by every artist in order to preserve the style of the body of the work in translation.

It should be noted that no theoretical approach to this problem has yet developed a single rule for the translation of realities, because translation is a creative process and such an idea is not expected. We would also like to suggest ways to overcome various random obstacles that may occur in practice in the translation of specific words by expressing our scientific-critical views and conclusions on this topic. In order to restore the original words in the language of translation, in our opinion, it is necessary to take into account the following:

- genre of the work;
- the function of the specific word in the text, the load of meaning;
- the relationship of original words in the original language and the language of translation;
- peculiarities of original and translated languages;
- their ability to form words, literary traditions, the level of comprehensibility of the word included in the language of translation.

Turning realities into context, not only figuratively, but also in material terms, using a variety of methods and taking into account their characteristics, allows us to draw objective conclusions. In the process of translating the means by which peoples express the concepts of life into another language, first of all, they are gaining ground in a particular text.

It is necessary to define their methodological tasks, and then to choose expressions that are in line with them in a way that is acceptable to the criteria and culture of the language.

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